

STRESS VARIATIONS IN THE UZBEK AND ENGLISH INTERROGATIVE SENTENCES

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Abstract: Stress is a universal phenomenon that affects all languages and is an essential component of each phrase. In the literature on the two languages, stress is defined as the amount of force (or power of pronunciation) utilized to produce a syllable, and it is perceived as loudness or prominence. However, every attempt has been made to acquaint the reader with the nature of rhythm and the fundamental concepts of stress in different sentences. In this study, we have sought to respond to a number of research questions related to how stress the words and use intonation in order to differ question sentences' meaning.

Key words: Stress, speech sounds, intonation, segments, accents.

Introduction. Stress, together with lexical and grammatical components of a language, contributes to the construction of various communicative types of sentences and indicates a speaker's attitude regarding the quantity of what is spoken. It comes as no surprise that stress is an essential component of any sentence. Each sentence has its unique method of pronouncing it and putting the stress in various conditions. There is no sentence and word that is not stressed. That is why, according to British phonetician Roger Kingdom, "if speech sounds are the body of a language, intonation is its soul." They have been some researches on the study of stress in different types of sentences in English in comparison with other languages. However comparative assessments of stress in interrogative sentences in Uzbek and English were not performed until now. Second, because stress is a fundamental component of speech, it is crucial to grasp the nature of stress in both Uzbek and English. As a result, we can state that the conclusion produced at the end of the dissertation is quite innovative and will be very valuable for students and investigators to utilize in their course papers and teaching materials. The preceding facts demonstrate the veracity of our investigation.

Cruttenden, on the other hand, avoids using the word "stress." Instead, the term "prominence" refers to segments or syllables, while "sonority" refers to "the carrying force of particular sounds" and "accent" refers to "those syllables that stand out above others". Cutler, on the other hand, defines stress as "the stress of syllables inside phrases or words within sentences." The current thesis focuses on the accentuation of syllables within words, often known as lexical stress.

Furthermore, there are generally more levels or degrees of prominence present in a word than just two, and the intermediary levels must also be considered. As a result, distinguishing between stressed and unstressed syllables is not usually enough for stress analysis.

There are various sound qualities, or correlates, for stress perception that allow us to identify when a syllable is stressed. There are four such correlates in English. Prominence is one of these qualities that all stressed syllables contain. A syllable is recognized as important in English due to four main criteria or correlates. The first of these variables is loudness. If a series of identical syllables is repeated, the syllable that is louder than the others is seen as stressed. The length of a syllable is another characteristic that aids in recognizing a stressed

syllable. Longer syllables are more likely to be seen as stressed. Pitch, which is described as "the perceptual correlate of the frequency of a sound—in speech, of the fundamental frequency of the vocal folds," is the third crucial element. When one syllable has a lower pitch than the rest of the syllables (which have a higher pitch, for example), the low-pitched syllable becomes more apparent. Pitch movement on a syllable, such as rising or falling, has a bigger impact on the prominence of that syllable. Quality is the fourth and final criterion that determines a syllable's prominence in English. When a syllable has a vowel with a different quality than vowels in other syllables, that syllable becomes prominent and, as a result, is interpreted as stressed.

There are 3 functions of word stress:

1. Word-stress has a constitutive function, as it moulds syllables into a word forming its stress pattern. A word does not exist without word stress because it organizes the syllables of a word into a language unit with a definite accentual structure, which is a pattern of relationship among the syllables. As a result, the word stress serves as a constitutive element. When a sound continuum is broken into components and structured by word stress into words, it becomes a phrase.

2. Word-stress has a distinctive function in English, because exists their different words in English with analogous sound structure which are differentiated in speech only by their stress pattern. Word stress is capable of distinguishing the meaning of words or their shapes on its own, which is how it performs its distinct role. Oppositions are formed by the accentual patterns of words or the degrees of word stress and their placements. E.g.:

noun / adjective verb

'Insult in'sult

'Subject sub'ject

'Import — im'port

'Billow — below

3. Word-stress has an identificatory function, because stress patterns of words enable people to identify definite combinations of sounds as meaningful linguistic units. A distortion of the stress pattern may hamper understanding or produce a strange accent. A person can recognize a series of syllables as a distinct accentual pattern of a word using word stress. This is referred to as the identificatory function of word stress (or cognitive). Correct accentuation facilitates communication for the listener, whereas a distorted accentual pattern of words and misplaced word stresses obstruct normal comprehension.

Sentence stress is the most important aspect of English intonation. Intonation organizes words into sentences, differentiates between sentence patterns, and adds emotional hue to utterances. Sentence stress is a significant component of English intonation that emphasizes certain words inside a sentence. Intonation groups words into sentences, differentiates between different sorts of sentences, and gives utterances an emotional tint. Learners find English intonation challenging. To master English intonation, one must first have the capacity to hear, understand, and replicate sentence stress in speech.

The content words, such as nouns, verbs, adjectives, and question words, are stressed when speaking a phrase since they convey the meaning. On the other hand, function words like articles and prepositions are not stressed. The following are the essential rules for sentence stress:

1. The content terms are highlighted
2. Unstressed structure words
3. The time between stressed words is always the same.

Sentence-stress is the one of the important aspects of intonation. Its primary duties are to identify words in a sentence based on their relative semantic value and to produce an appropriate rhythmical framework for a sentence. Sentence stress occurs on a syllable, but it also distinguishes rhythmic groups, syntagmas, sentences, and sentence units.

Conclusion. We attempted to thoroughly describe and clarify our theme in our dissertation. As stated in the introduction, phonological elements such as stress and intonation are universal to all languages; there is no such thing as a monotonous language. Every day, we utilize many stress contours and components to describe our emotions and feelings, as well as our circumstances, such as rage, wish, happiness, irony, agreement, disagreement, sadness, delight, and others. But we don't think about stress placement or how to use its components; individuals don't learn stress and its features, idiosyncrasies to convey their utilization in everyday speech because they learned it in childhood without teaching or studying. Stress patterns are fairly similar in various languages, and I believe this is because most people's feelings are similar. However, they differ in terms of stress placement. Their own characteristics, quirks, which we cannot dispute that intonation is dependent on the user or speaker. Because some individuals are full of passion and are impressed by everything, they feel everything deeply, and their speech is usually emotive, colorful, and impressive, while others are very cold, unimpressive, unemotional, and different. Europeans have thought that eastern people are very emotional and spectacular, and that their speech was likewise dramatic and colorful, but regrettably, phonological features of the Uzbek language in terms of stress placement, as with all Turkic languages, are rarely studied. We can glean little information from the written works, but we make every effort to thoroughly investigate the subject.

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